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Europe, physical space or abstract concept?

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Introduction

Europe is a continent which has a boundary with Asia. Europe has the Council of Europe which aims to protect human rights and democracy, promote European culture and traditions. Among the continent, there is a Union which unites many countries. Most of the countries in Europe are members of the European Union.

The European Union is an economic and political union that encompasses 28 European countries and covers most of the continent. The EU has created harmonised legislation for its Member States, has an internal market and four freedoms for its Members, has established a single currency and created the Schengen area. The EU promotes human rights, human dignity, equality, freedom and democracy. The European Union has the features of both an international organization and a state.¹ On one hand, a state is a free-standing entity with territory, sovereignty, independence and legitimacy, on the other hand an international organization is a body that has been founded on voluntary cooperation, communal management and joint-decision making.² The European Union nowadays strives towards harmonising laws and regulations in its Member States and strengthening the internal market.

History

The European Union has not always been as big as it is today. Currently, there are 28 Member States in the European Union. The last one to join the EU was Croatia in 2013. The European Union is based on two Treaties, the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and the Treaty on European Union. However, it all started with a proposal and only five participating countries. The European integration and the idea of a united Europe started with a proposal by Robert Schuman in an attempt to restabilize relations between France and Germany which led to the European Coal and Steel Community and the Treaty was signed by France, Germany, Italy, Belgium, Netherlands and Luxembourg in 1951 to establish a

¹ McCormick, J. (2010). *Understanding the European Union : A Concise Introduction*. 5th ed. Palgrave Macmillan Ltd, 14-15.

² *Ibid*, 4.

common market in coal and steel.³ These six countries are known as the Founding Fathers of the European Union. During the development of the European Union, several Treaties were drafted and signed. The Rome Treaty established the European Economic Community with the aim of establishing a common market, promoting closer relations between the Member States and abolishing customs duties.⁴ The Single European Act changed the common market to internal market and defined the internal market as an area without internal barriers in which the free movement of goods, services, persons and capital must be ensured.⁵ Today these are known as the four freedoms of the European Union. In 1992 the Maastricht Treaty was signed, which changed the European Community to the European Union, created the three-pillar structure and made many substantive changes. The Maastricht Treaty became the Treaty on European Union. The first pillar was the European Community, second the Common Foreign and Security Policy and third the Justice and Home Affairs. The Treaty on European Union established the principle of subsidiarity, in addition, it created the concept of European citizenship and led to the adoption of the single currency, the Euro.⁶ There was an enlargement after the Treaty when additional countries signed the Treaty and became the Member States of the European Union. The Amsterdam Treaty in 1997 extended the co-decision procedure and the Nice Treaty in 2001 adopted the Charter of Fundamental Rights. There were already 25 Member States after the Nice Treaty. The Lisbon Treaty in 2007 was the last one and amended the Rome Treaty which became the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. In addition, the Charter of Fundamental Rights became legally binding.

Integrating area

The integration is a process where industrial, political, legal, economic, cultural policies have been harmonised wholly or partially in the European Union. The European Union has become from simply a free trade area into a monetary and political union where economic and political policies have been harmonised, the further aim is to harmonise all policies. Joining the European Union is not simple, it is a complex procedure and requires a lot of time, since it is necessary to meet the conditions set by the EU and implement the EU

³ Craig, P., De Burca, G. (2011). EU law text, cases and materials. 5th ed. New York: Oxford University Press, 5.

⁴ *Ibid*, 6.

⁵ Craig, *supra nota* 3, 11.

⁶ *Ibid*, 14.

rules and regulations, including the adoption of the Euro.⁷ There are a few countries that are in the process of integrating the EU legislation into their national law.

The European Union is standing in front of challenges and difficulties. Attacks, religious extremism, unrest and wars lead to the establishment of a new security policy, the EU faces the refugee crisis, environmental issues, including climate change, still cause concern. The European Union adopted a 10-year strategy, Europe 2020, in 2010 in order to enhance economic growth and employment, objectives are in 5 main areas including education, employment, innovation, climate change and poverty.⁸ The European Union has put a lot of effort into establishing an environmental legislation in order to protect and uphold the environment, reduce pollution and the use of toxic or hazardous substances. However, many challenges still exist and the EU is planning to tackle them and has adopted a programme that will be guiding European environment policy until 2020 in order to protect the natural capital, improve the resource efficiency and decrease environment-related risks to people's health and wellbeing.⁹ The refugee crisis is at its peak and the EU needs to find a solution. Hence, the EU has adopted many plans and agendas how to tackle the migration and refugee issues. For example, the European Commission has drafted an agenda to develop steps in order to manage the refugee crisis.¹⁰ In 2016 the news about the United Kingdom planning to leave the EU was a shock. The UK has had a huge influence on the EU law and court decisions. It was the first time a State has used the Article 50 of the Treaty on the European Union to leave the EU. However, the decision can still be revoked and nothing is sure yet. The EU has many issues that need to be solved, however, many helpful regulations, agendas, manuals have been adopted to tackle the issues and make the EU even better and stronger.

⁷ European Union. *About the EU*. Accessible: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/countries_en#schengen, 25 September 2017.

⁸ Government of the Netherlands. *Europe 2020*. Accessible: <https://www.government.nl/topics/european-union/europe-2020>, 25 September 2017.

⁹ European Commission. *Environment Action Programme to 2020*. Accessible: <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/action-programme/>, 26 September 2017.

¹⁰ European Commission. *Managing the refugee crisis*. Accessible: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/background-information/docs/eam_state_of_play_20151014_priority_actions_en.pdf, 29 September 2017.

Conclusions

The EU is based on common policies which are based on common legislation. The EU has adopted regulations and directives in order to harmonise the laws of its Member States. Member States should have common policies so that they would be united and move towards the same goal. Common policies are shaped by EU legislative acts and therefore a legal system is necessary in the Europe. Common policies are binding on the Member States.

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